

Lab tips, tricks and hacks:

Finding a cost-effective optical system to identify 2D materials

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Two-dimensional materials, such as graphene and transition metal dichalcogenides, have garnered significant attention in recent years due to their unique properties and potential applications in electronics, energy storage, and other fields. Optical microscopes, with their large throughput and non-destructive nature are essential tools to quickly find ultra thin flakes of 2D materials and to distinguish them from very thick ones. However, the cost of optical microscopes can be a significant threshold for research groups with limited budgets. In this technical note, we present our efforts to find an inexpensive optical microscope system for labs with limited budgets. We compared the image quality of three different standard optical microscopes and we also discuss the use of zoom lens systems for flake identification. For labs running with low budget we recommend a homebuilt system based on a zoom-lens system that can be used both as system to identify flakes and as a deterministic placement setup. We believe that this comparison will be very useful for labs with limited budgets that are looking to study two-dimensional materials and develop new technologies based on them.

Optical microscopes play a crucial role in the research of two-dimensional materials, such as graphene and transition metal dichalcogenides. These materials, which are just a few atoms thick, have unique properties and are of great interest for a variety of applications. Optical microscopes, and especially metallurgical microscopes that feature both transmission and epi-illumination, are particularly useful in the identification of mechanically exfoliated two-dimensional materials, as they allow scientists to quickly and non-destructively assess the thickness of these materials and search for them over large areas. As a

result, optical microscopes are essential tools to carry out experimental research on mechanically exfoliated 2D materials.

However, it's worth noting that metallurgical microscopes can be quite expensive, which can be a significant threshold for research groups with limited budgets.

Our research group has been working to find an inexpensive optical microscope system for labs with limited budgets that are interested in studying two-dimensional materials. We have studied three different standard optical microscopes and also three different homebuilt systems based on zoom lenses. Figure 1 shows optical images of the different optical systems tested to find and identify mechanically exfoliated 2D materials.

Figure 1. Pictures of the different optical systems tested for finding 2D materials produced by mechanical exfoliation. (a) A [Nikon Eclipse LV100](#) metallurgical microscope (~15 000 €). (b) A [Motic BA310 MET-T](#) metallurgical microscope (~4 500 €). (c) A [Swift SW350T](#) biological microscope, retrofitted to allow epi-illumination imaging (~ 350 €). (d) to (f) Homebuilt optical systems based on coaxial illumination zoom lenses system. (d) Based on an [OPTEM Fusion 7:1 zoom lens](#) (~2 000 €). (e) Based on an [Aliexpress zoom equipped with a turret](#) with 5x, 10x and 20x PLAN Achromatic objectives (~900 €). (f) Based on an [Aliexpress coaxial zoom lens \(0.7x – 4.5x\)](#) equipped with a 10x objective lens (~600 €).

To validate the performance of these systems, we have compared the images of the same flakes (mechanically exfoliated single-layer and few-layer MoS₂) using the different optical microscopy systems. Figure 2 shows the resulting images. Based on our experience the Motic BA310 MET-T microscope offers very good image quality at a portion of the price of the Nikon Eclipse LV100. We thus believe that the Motic offers a good trade-off between image quality and cost. The retrofitted Swift SW350 microscope image quality is substantially worse and it might be not enough to identify flakes effectively in a research environment. When finding an even more cost-effective option than the Motic BA310 MET-T, we suggest taking a look to the homebuilt systems based on zoom lenses with coaxial illumination. Within these systems we found that the one shown in Figure 1e presents a very good image quality at a very moderate cost.

It is important to mention that we found that the attached camera can have a very important role in the image quality. While inexpensive [Aliexpress C-mount cameras](#) (~60 Eur) are probably good enough for flake identification tasks, more professional microscopy cameras like the [AMScope MU1803](#) (~400 Eur) provides much better image quality and it allows for a much wider degree of parameter adjustment during acquisition. In Figure 3 we provide another comparison of the same mechanically exfoliated single- and few-layer MoS₂ flake with different optical systems but now using the same AMScope MU1803 camera in all cases. One can now distinguish better how the homebuilt system shown in Figure 1e provides a very good quality despite of the reduced cost.

Figure 2. Optical microscopy images of the same few-layer MoS₂ flake on SiO₂/Si acquired with different optical systems in the laboratory. Note that for the Swift microscope system the picture has been acquired with the camera of a smartphone through the eyepiece of the microscope.

Figure 3. Optical microscopy images of the same few-layer MoS₂ flake on SiO₂/Si acquired with different optical systems in the laboratory but using the same camera.

Figure 4. Transmission mode optical microscopy images of the same few-layer MoS₂ flake on a Gel-Film substrate acquired with different optical systems in the laboratory. Note that for the Swift microscope system the picture has been acquired with the camera of a smartphone through the eyepiece of the microscope.

In the following Table we provide the components to reproduce the system displayed in Figure 1e. The whole system can be reproduced by less than 1000 €. This system has the advantage that it can be used, with minimum modifications, as a deterministic transfer setup (Figure 1e shows it with the stages used for deterministic transfer). Thus, this kind of zoom lens based optical system to find flakes can be very convenient for labs with moderate budget as they can use the same system to find the flakes and to perform deterministic transfers.

DESCRIPTION	VENDOR	LINK	PRICE (€)
Post	Thorlabs	RS300/M	61.98
Base for post	Thorlabs	PB1	25.61
Aluminum breadboard	Thorlabs	MB2025/M	119.63
Focusing stage for zoom lens	Aliexpress	Aliexpress	60.08
Adaptor 76 mm to 50 mm (to adapt zoom lens to focusing stage)	Aliexpress	Aliexpress	10.19
Coaxial zoom lens with turret and LED illuminator	Aliexpress	Aliexpress	465.92
Rubber feet	Amazon	Amazon	8.99
XY stage	Amazon	Amazon	53.67
Camera*	Aliexpress	Aliexpress	59.82
22' monitor	Amazon	Amazon	80.99
Plate illuminator (for transmission light measurements)	Aliexpress	Aliexpress	51.73
		TOTAL	998.61

*As shown in Figure 3, a better image quality is obtained with more expensive microscope cameras like the MU1803 (~400 Eur)